

Rethinking the School Day for Healthier Brains, Calmer Classrooms and Safer Communities

Professor Ken Purnell

Head of Educational Neuroscience, CQUniversity Australia

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The two minute overview video is available at <https://share.descript.com/view/3jrNtQ9oKRJ>

Abstract

Adolescent behavioural problems in schools and communities are often attributed to poor character or motivation, yet accumulating neuroscience evidence shows that many difficulties are consistent with a structural misalignment between traditional school timetables and adolescents' circadian biology. This paper reviews empirical evidence on adolescent sleep-wake patterns, circadian phase delay, ultradian rhythms, and their effects on learning, behaviour, and mental health. Delayed school start times consistently increase sleep duration and reduce tardiness, absenteeism, behaviour referrals, and risk behaviours, with modest academic gains. However, shifting start times by only 20–30 minutes is unlikely to be sufficient (this threshold is based on the author's interpretation of evidence showing greatest gains at 8.30 a.m. or later). Drawing on chronobiology and cognitive neuroscience, the paper proposes an extended-day model that incorporates 90-minute learning blocks aligned with ultradian cycles, flexible arrival and departure windows, and community partnerships. Implementation requires coordinated action by policymakers, school leaders, transport authorities, and families. Critically, adults—including politicians and community leaders—must scaffold adolescents' decision-making by helping them understand consequences, plan effectively, and take ownership of their choices, mirroring effective parenting strategies that balance autonomy support with structure. The paper concludes that redesigning school hours is an evidence-based public health and educational intervention with potential to reduce misbehaviour, improve wellbeing, and contribute to safer communities.

Introduction

Teenagers are often criticised for struggling with early mornings, poor behaviour, and impulsive decision-making. Common explanations invoke laziness, defiance, or inadequate parenting. Yet neuroscience tells a different story. Adolescent sleep-wake patterns undergo profound biological changes driven by circadian phase delay, in which melatonin secretion and sleep onset shift approximately 1.5–2.5 hours later than in childhood or adulthood (Crowley et al., 2018; Hagenauer et al., 2009). When schools require early starts, often before 8.00 a.m., adolescents are forced to wake during a biological "night", leading to chronic sleep restriction that undermines cognitive control, emotional regulation, and behavioural inhibition (Carskadon, 2011; Walker, 2017).

This mismatch between institutional schedules and developmental biology has measurable consequences. Systematic reviews and policy statements from major paediatric bodies show that delayed school start times reliably increase nightly sleep duration, reduce tardiness and absenteeism, lower rates of depressive symptoms, decrease behaviour referrals, and modestly improve academic performance (American Academy of Pediatrics, 2014; Minges & Redline, 2016; Wheaton et al., 2016). Yet most secondary schools worldwide continue to operate timetables designed for adult convenience and historical constraints rather than adolescent neurobiology (International Bureau of Education–UNESCO, 2022).

This paper examines evidence on adolescent circadian and ultradian rhythms, their effects on behaviour and learning, and the outcomes of school start time reforms. It then proposes an extended-day timetable model that aligns academic scheduling with biological rhythms, incorporates structured support and community engagement, and addresses implementation barriers. It is argued that successful reform requires adults, including policymakers, educators, parents, and community leaders, to actively scaffold adolescent decision-making, helping

teenagers understand consequences, plan ahead, and take ownership of their choices. The analysis draws on recent work integrating educational neuroscience with cognitive load theory and learning design (Purnell, 2026a, 2026b).

Adolescent Circadian Biology and Sleep Needs

Circadian Phase Delay

The circadian system is the brain's internal 24-hour clock, regulated by the suprachiasmatic nucleus in the hypothalamus and synchronised to external light-dark cycles via melatonin secretion from the pineal gland (Crowley et al., 2018). During puberty, the timing of melatonin release shifts later by approximately 1.5–2.5 hours, a phenomenon termed circadian phase delay (Hagenauer et al., 2009). This delay is driven by maturational changes in the circadian pacemaker, altered sensitivity to evening light, and a slower accumulation of homeostatic sleep pressure throughout the day (Crowley et al., 2018). As a result, adolescents have difficulty falling asleep before 11.00 p.m. and naturally wake later in the morning, typically around 8.00–9.00 a.m. (Carskadon, 2011; International Bureau of Education–UNESCO, 2022).

Sleep Duration and Restriction

Despite requiring 8–10 hours of sleep per night for optimal functioning (American Academy of Pediatrics, 2014), most adolescents get only 6–7 hours on school nights when start times are early (Minges & Redline, 2016). This chronic sleep restriction stems from the clash between biologically delayed sleep onset and socially imposed early wake times. Sleep deprivation in adolescence has been associated with impaired attention, working memory, and executive function; increased emotional reactivity and irritability; higher rates of anxiety, depression, and suicidal ideation; and elevated risk-taking behaviours, including substance use, reckless driving, and aggression (Carskadon, 2011; International Bureau of Education–UNESCO, 2022; Walker, 2017).

Critically, sleep restriction during adolescence affects not only daytime functioning but also long-term neurodevelopment. Slow-wave sleep and rapid eye movement (REM) sleep—both of which are reduced by early wake times—play important roles in synaptic pruning, memory consolidation, and emotional processing (Walker, 2017). Chronic deprivation of these sleep stages may have lasting effects on cognitive and mental health trajectories.

Ultradian Rhythms and Learning Efficiency

Beyond circadian rhythms, the brain operates on shorter cycles known as ultradian rhythms, which recur multiple times throughout the day (Kleitman, 1963). Research on cognitive performance and attention indicates that focused mental work tends to follow approximately 90-minute cycles of high and low alertness, corresponding to oscillations in cortical arousal and autonomic activity, though the evidence for distinct ultradian alertness cycles during waking hours is less robust than for nocturnal sleep cycles (Schmidt et al., 2007). Performance on complex cognitive tasks peaks within the first 60–90 minutes of sustained effort and then declines as mental fatigue accumulates (Ericsson et al., 1993).

These findings suggest that timetables organised into 90-minute learning blocks, interspersed with 10–20-minute recovery breaks, may optimise attention, reduce cognitive overload, and support more efficient learning than traditional 45–50-minute periods stacked back-to-back without genuine rest (Ericsson et al., 1993; Schmidt et al., 2007). Standard timetables that require adolescents to transition rapidly between subjects in crowded corridors, with minimal opportunity for physical movement or mental recovery, are likely to increase off-task behaviour, conflict, and disengagement, particularly during periods of low circadian alertness (Carskadon, 2011; Walker, 2017).

Evidence from School Start Time Reforms

Sleep and Wellbeing Outcomes

A systematic review of experimental and quasi-experimental studies found that delaying school start times by 25–77 minutes consistently increased total sleep time, with the greatest gains when start times shifted to 8.30 a.m. or later (Minges & Redline, 2016). Students reported reduced daytime sleepiness, lower caffeine consumption, and fewer depressive symptoms after delays (Minges & Redline, 2016; Wahlstrom et al., 2014). A natural-experiment study in Seattle found that when high school start times moved from 7.50 a.m. to 8.45 a.m., students gained an average of 34 additional minutes of sleep per night and showed improved alertness and mood (Dunster et al., 2018).

Behaviour and Attendance

Multiple studies report reductions in tardiness, unexcused absences, and disciplinary referrals following delayed start times (Dunster et al., 2018; Wahlstrom et al., 2014). In the Seattle study, later start times were associated with a 14% lower probability of behaviour referrals (Dunster et al., 2018). A four-year longitudinal evaluation in a large American school district found that later high school start times were linked to improved attendance, higher graduation rates, and fewer suspensions, with particularly pronounced benefits for economically disadvantaged and minority students (Wahlstrom et al., 2022). The same study also reported reductions in self-reported risk behaviours, including weapon carrying, physical fighting, and substance use (Wahlstrom et al., 2022).

Academic Performance

Effects on academic outcomes are statistically significant but more modest than those on behaviour and wellbeing. Delayed start times are associated with small increases in grade point averages, standardised test scores, and course completion rates (Dunster et al., 2018; Minges & Redline, 2016; Thacher & Onyper, 2016). The magnitude of academic gains varies across studies and appears to depend on the extent of sleep increase, baseline sleep debt, and concurrent factors such as homework load and pre-bed screen time (Carskadon, 2011; Walker, 2017).

Community and Safety Impacts

Later start times have been linked with reduced adolescent car crash rates in some jurisdictions (American Academy of Pediatrics, 2014; Wheaton et al., 2016), though the precise mechanisms are not yet established. Emerging evidence also suggests that aligning school schedules with adolescent biology may reduce community-level risk behaviours, especially among vulnerable groups (Wahlstrom et al., 2022).

Proposed Extended-Day Model Aligned with Adolescent Biology

Design Principles

Evidence supports later start times but simply shifting the school day by 20–30 minutes is unlikely to be sufficient. A comprehensive approach requires integrating circadian science, ultradian rhythm research, and cognitive load theory to redesign when and how learning is scheduled. The following model is proposed as an evidence-informed framework, recognising that local adaptation will be necessary.

Core Principles:

Circadian Alignment: Begin high-demand academic learning no earlier than 9:30 a.m., allowing adolescents a realistic opportunity for 8–9 hours of sleep that aligns with biologically delayed sleep-wake patterns (American Academy of Pediatrics, 2014; International Bureau of Education–UNESCO, 2022).

Ultradian Block Scheduling: Structure the day into 90-minute learning blocks for cognitively demanding tasks (mathematics, science, extended writing, and problem-solving), with 15–20-minute recovery breaks between blocks (Ericsson et al., 1993; Kleitman, 1963; Schmidt et al., 2007).

Flexible Extensions: Offer optional early-arrival and late-departure windows for supervised breakfast, tutoring, wellbeing support, enrichment activities, sport, and community partnerships, thereby reducing the rigidity of "one bell for all" (Wahlstrom et al., 2022; Wheaton et al., 2016).

Behavioural Scaffolding: Organise staffing and supervision so that the highest-risk periods for misbehaviour—early mornings, unstructured transitions, and late afternoons—are characterised by purposeful activity and supportive adult presence rather than passive "holding" supervision (Wahlstrom et al., 2022; Wheaton et al., 2016).

Example Timetable Structure

The following structure outlines one possible implementation for a secondary school serving students aged 13–18. Times and durations may be adjusted to suit local transport, staffing, and community constraints.

8.30–9.30 a.m.: Optional Early Arrival Window

Voluntary attendance. Activities include supervised breakfast club, quiet study, physical activity (gymnasium and outdoor spaces), music practice, art studio access, and individual wellbeing check-ins with pastoral staff. This period accommodates students whose family or transport circumstances require early arrival, while avoiding the sleep deprivation caused by compulsory early classes.

Block 1 (High-Demand Learning): 9.30–11.00 a.m.

90 minutes of focused academic instruction in subjects requiring sustained cognitive effort: advanced mathematics, laboratory sciences, foreign languages, analytical writing, complex problem-solving. Students are at peak circadian alertness; lessons emphasise depth over breadth, minimising extraneous cognitive load and supporting schema construction (Purnell, 2026b; Sweller et al., 2019).

11.00–11.20 a.m.: Break 1

20 minutes for nutrition, movement, social interaction, and brief quiet options (library, courtyard seating). Deliberate recovery period aligned with ultradian cycle research (Ericsson et al., 1993; Schmidt et al., 2007).

Block 2 (High-Demand Learning, Different Domain): 11.20 a.m.–12.50 p.m.

90 minutes in a second cognitively demanding subject area. Timetabling should avoid consecutive blocks within the same discipline (e.g., mathematics followed by physics) to reduce interference and support varied retrieval practice (Purnell, 2026a).

12.50–1.30 p.m.: Lunch and Unstructured Time

40 minutes for eating, socialising, and unstructured play or rest. Adequate mealtimes support nutrition and social development; longer breaks are associated with fewer afternoon behaviour incidents (Wahlstrom et al., 2014).

Block 3 (Applied and Practical Learning): 1.30–3.00 p.m.

90-minute sessions for subjects emphasising application, creativity, and collaboration: vocational education and training, design and technology, creative arts, physical education, project-based learning, and community service learning. The afternoon circadian dip in alertness is better suited to physically active or socially collaborative learning than to high-stakes abstract reasoning (Carskadon, 2011; Schmidt et al., 2007).

3.00–3.20 p.m.: Break 2

20 minutes of physical activity (a short walk, sport, or stretching) or a quiet mental reset. Research on sustained attention indicates that brief physical activity after prolonged cognitive work enhances subsequent focus and reduces fatigue (Ericsson et al., 1993).

Block 4 (Extension and Support): 3.20–4.30 p.m.

Flexible attendance pattern throughout the week. Options include targeted tutoring and homework support, curriculum enrichment (coding, debating, advanced science), competitive and recreational sport, visual and performing arts clubs, work-based learning placements, and partnerships with community organisations (youth services, environmental groups, cultural institutions). Students attend according to individual learning plans, interests, and identified needs. Staffing combines teachers, teaching assistants, community volunteers, and external partners, reducing costs and increasing relevance.

Rationale and Expected Outcomes

This model shifts the "core" instructional day to 9.30 a.m.–3.00 p.m., with flexible extensions before and after. By aligning high-demand academic work with peak circadian alertness and structuring learning in 90-minute blocks, the timetable respects circadian and ultradian biology. Optional early and late periods reduce conflicts between family logistics and adolescent sleep needs, while providing structured, supervised activities during periods that currently see elevated rates of youth misbehaviour and risk-taking in the community (Wahlstrom et al., 2022).

Expected outcomes, based on existing start-time research and chronobiological principles, include increased nightly sleep duration, reduced tardiness and absenteeism, fewer classroom behaviour incidents, lower rates of anxiety and depressive symptoms, improved attention and engagement in lessons, modest academic gains, and reduced community risk behaviours (American Academy of Pediatrics, 2014; Dunster et al., 2018; International Bureau of Education–UNESCO, 2022; Minges & Redline, 2016; Wahlstrom et al., 2022).

Adolescent Decision-Making and the Role of Adult Scaffolding

Beyond structural reforms to timetables, effective implementation also depends on how adolescents and communities engage with change—a question that requires attention to adolescent decision-making neuroscience.

Neuroscience of Adolescent Decision-Making

Adolescence is characterised by significant reorganisation of brain systems involved in decision-making, reward processing, and impulse control. The prefrontal cortex—particularly dorsolateral regions responsible for planning, working memory, abstract reasoning, and weighing long-term consequences—undergoes protracted development that extends into the mid-20s (Blakemore & Robbins, 2012; Casey et al., 2019). By contrast, subcortical structures, including the striatum and amygdala, which mediate reward sensitivity and emotional reactivity, mature earlier and show heightened responsiveness during adolescence (Casey et al., 2019).

This asynchrony creates a developmental window in which reward-seeking and affective impulses are heightened, while cognitive control and strategic decision-making are still maturing (Blakemore & Robbins, 2012). Adolescents are more likely than adults to discount delayed rewards, tolerate uncertainty, and make risky choices, particularly under peer influence or emotional arousal (Defoe et al., 2015). However, with time to deliberate, access to relevant information, and supportive guidance, adolescents can reason soundly and learn to anticipate consequences and plan effectively (Casey et al., 2019).

Parental Autonomy Support and Scaffolded Decision-Making

Research on parenting and adolescent development shows that effective support balances autonomy-granting with structure and guidance (Soenens & Vansteenkiste, 2010). Autonomy-supportive parents encourage adolescents to articulate their perspectives, explore options, and make choices, while providing information about consequences, modelling decision-making

processes, and setting clear boundaries. Recent educational neuroscience work emphasises that supporting learners, whether children or adolescents, requires understanding how brain architecture constrains and enables learning and designing environments that align with those constraints (Purnell, 2026a, 2026b). This approach, often termed *scaffolding*, helps adolescents develop competence in planning, risk assessment, and self-regulation without prematurely withdrawing adult oversight (Soenens & Vansteenkiste, 2010).

Critically, autonomy support is distinct from permissiveness. Effective scaffolding involves active parental engagement: asking questions that prompt adolescents to consider consequences, providing information to inform decisions, discussing potential outcomes, and allowing adolescents to experience manageable challenges while remaining available to assist. Research shows that adolescents whose parents use autonomy-supportive strategies report higher self-confidence, better academic outcomes, greater psychological wellbeing, and lower rates of risky behaviours than peers whose parents are either highly controlling or disengaged (Soenens & Vansteenkiste, 2010).

Implications for Policy and Community Leadership

The same principles apply to how communities, policymakers, and school leaders support adolescents' decision-making about school timetables, sleep, and behaviour. Teenagers are often told to "just go to bed earlier" or "stop being lazy", yet they are rarely given the information, environmental conditions, or adult support needed to make informed choices about sleep and time management.

Adults in positions of authority, such as politicians, school administrators, health professionals, parents, must step up as effective parents do: by helping adolescents understand the biological, cognitive, and emotional consequences of sleep deprivation; by creating environments (timetables, home routines, community spaces) that make healthy choices realistic rather than heroic; by involving adolescents in discussions about scheduling reforms and by respecting their input; and by modelling deliberate planning and long-term thinking (American Academy of Pediatrics, 2014; Casey et al., 2019). Understanding how adolescent brains process information, manage cognitive load, and respond to environmental cues is foundational to designing systems, whether educational, familial, or policy-based, that support rather than undermine development (Purnell, 2026a, 2026b).

When schools delay start times and clearly explain to students why the change matters by linking it to brain development, learning efficiency, and mental health, adolescents are better placed to take ownership of sleep hygiene, reduce late-night screen time, and manage their evening schedules (Purnell, 2026a; Walker, 2017). When policymakers involve young people in consultations about timetable reforms rather than imposing changes paternalistically, adolescents are more likely to understand the rationale, support the policy, and adapt their behaviour accordingly (Soenens & Vansteenkiste, 2010).

Effective adult scaffolding means recognising adolescents as capable agents whose decision-making systems are under construction, and providing the information, structure, and autonomy support they need to develop competence in planning, self-regulation, and anticipating consequences. This is not indulgence; it is developmentally appropriate pedagogy extended to policy (Casey et al., 2019).

Implementation Barriers and Solutions

Transport and Logistics

School transport is often cited as the primary barrier to delayed start times (Wahlstrom et al., 2014). Many districts use staggered schedules to reduce bus fleet costs, with high schools starting earliest to allow buses to complete multiple runs. However, recent optimisation research shows that later secondary start times are logistically feasible if districts adjust elementary schedules, reorganise routes, or modestly increase transport budgets (Bloom et al., 2019). Some districts

have successfully implemented later starts while reducing total transport costs through improved routing algorithms and greater route efficiency (Bloom et al., 2019).

Staffing and Supervision

Extended-day models require a rethink of staffing structures. Rather than expecting all teachers to be present from 8.30 a.m. to 4.30 p.m., schools can use staggered shifts, part-time staff, teaching assistants, and community partners to supervise optional early and late blocks (Wahlstrom et al., 2014). This approach can reduce costs compared with traditional models while expanding the range of learning opportunities available to students.

Family and Work Schedules

Childcare and parental work schedules are common concerns, particularly for families with children in both primary and secondary schools. Extended-day models with flexible arrival and departure windows help address this by allowing families to drop off students earlier or collect them later, without forcing all adolescents into a single rigid schedule (Bloom et al., 2019; Wahlstrom et al., 2014).

Extracurricular Activities and Part-Time Work

Later school finish times may conflict with sport, part-time employment, and family commitments. However, evidence from schools that have implemented later starts indicates that adolescents and families adapt within one to two school semesters, and that wellbeing benefits outweigh logistical inconveniences (Dunster et al., 2018; Wahlstrom et al., 2014). Moreover, scheduling high-demand academic learning earlier in the day and reserving later blocks for flexible, applied, and community-based learning can reduce homework loads and create time for extracurricular engagement without resorting to late-night study (Wahlstrom et al., 2014).

Policy and Advocacy

Successful implementation requires coordinated action by education departments, transport authorities, health services, and community organisations. State or national guidelines recommending start times no earlier than 8.30 a.m. for secondary schools which aligns with the aligned with American Academy of Pediatrics recommendations, provide legitimacy for local reforms (American Academy of Pediatrics, 2014; International Bureau of Education–UNESCO, 2022). Pilot programmes with robust evaluation frameworks can demonstrate feasibility, document outcomes, and build evidence for wider adoption (Dunster et al., 2018; Wahlstrom et al., 2022).

Conclusion

Adolescent behavioural problems are often attributed to character deficits, yet neuroscience shows that many difficulties arise from forcing teenagers to function during their biological night. Chronic sleep restriction from early school start times undermines attention, emotional regulation, impulse control, and mental health, with predictable consequences for behaviour in schools and communities. Delayed start times reliably increase sleep duration and reduce tardiness, absenteeism, behaviour referrals, and risk behaviours, while modestly improving academic performance. However, start-time delays alone are insufficient.

This paper proposes an extended-day timetable model that integrates circadian science, ultradian rhythm research, and cognitive load principles. It structures the school day into 90-minute learning blocks aligned with adolescent alertness patterns and offers flexible early- and late-period options for support, enrichment, and community engagement. Implementation requires systemic reform of transport, staffing, and policy, alongside genuine adolescent involvement in decision-making.

Critically, adults, including policymakers, school leaders, parents, and community members, must recognise their responsibility to scaffold adolescents' decision-making by helping teenagers

understand consequences, plan effectively, and take ownership of their choices. This means creating environments that make healthy sleep realistic, communicating clearly about the neuroscience underpinning scheduling reforms, and respecting adolescents as capable agents whose brains are still developing. Such an approach is not indulgence; it is evidence-based, developmentally appropriate policy that can reduce misbehaviour, improve wellbeing, and contribute to safer, more equitable communities.

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